

AIAL's comments for Targeted stakeholder consultation on the Commission's Draft Guidance on Article 73 AI Act - Incident Reporting (High-Risk AI Systems)

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ABOUT AIAL

The AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) is a dedicated research lab within Trinity College Dublin that is focused on ensuring that the wider AI ecology — from research and product development, to regulation — centres public interest, particularly, the most marginalised and disenfranchised in society. Our inquiries into AI accountability, therefore, span from studies of large systems, structures, and ecologies (such as the AI field itself and regulatory processes) to executions of audits and evaluations on specific AI models, tools, and training datasets. We recognize that AI accountability research is most impactful when it can inform the public, impacted groups, and policy makers. Thus, we aim for active policy translation of our (as well as field wide) research.

You can find more information about the AIAL on its website at <https://aial.ie/>.

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1. Introduction

This document represents the answers prepared by the team at AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) for the Targeted stakeholder consultation on the Commission's Draft Guidance on Article 73 AI Act - Incident Reporting (High-Risk AI Systems),¹ conducted by the European Commission's AI Office as part of its duties under the AI Act. The consultation was open from 26th September until 7th November 2025, during which the AIAL team submitted its response.²

This report provides an expanded version of the responses submitted during the consultation, with the intent to preserve their intended meaning while expanding on the details and clarifications as the original consultation imposed an extremely short character limit. The structure of the document follows the same format and order as the questions posed in the consultation, where each question is followed by the AIAL team's corresponding notes and responses. The content from the guidelines and the consultation forms is provided in a box along with the relevant paragraph number, with the AIAL's comments provided below it.

2. Definition - Incident & Malfunction

These comments relate to Question 2 within the consultation form.

(2) Second, it establishes clear accountability for providers, and to a certain extent as well users, of these systems, ensuring they take responsibility for the proper functioning and safety of their products

The role "users" should be changed to "deployers" as defined within the AI Act Article 3(4) to ensure there is no misinterpretation as "end-users" who may be lay people.

¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/consultations/ai-act-commission-issues-draft-guidance-and-reporting-template-serious-ai-incidents-and-seeks>

² The submitted response is available at <https://10.5281/zenodo.17559043>

Footnote 4: event describing the pure occurrence while the term incident describes the concrete result or manifestation of an event or an occurrence.

The phrasing should be changed to indicate "*event*" describes something that occurs, and which must meet certain requirements to be considered as an "*incident*". Typically, these requirements are defined in relevant legal frameworks such as NIS2 and the AI Act. This is aligned with concepts defined in common as well as legal language.

(8) while an event where the development or use of an AI system is potentially harmful is termed an "AI hazard".

It is important to distinguish "*hazard*" as it is used in risk management (e.g. ISO, CEN standards). The term "*hazard*" refers to "source of potential harm".³ This means that AI systems are to be considered a hazard when they themselves are the source of harm. This is distinct from harm arising from situations such as the AI systems malfunctioning, being misused, or being compromised.

(9) The wording of Article 3(49) AI Act "refers to an incident or malfunctioning" and implies that a malfunction is not considered to be an incident.

This is incorrect as the wording of Article 3(49) does not necessarily differentiate between incident and malfunctioning, but instead clarifies that both events apply. This can be evidenced from the phrasing of Article 3(14) regarding safety components which states "*or the failure or malfunction of which endangers the health and safety of persons or property*" and which can be found to be aligned with the meaning of "*serious incident*". This phrasing is also present in Recital 55 in two places, one of which states "*The failure or malfunctioning of such components might directly lead to risks to the physical integrity of critical infrastructure and thus to risks to health and safety of persons and property*", which is also aligned with the meaning of "*serious incident*". From this, it should be interpreted that the meaning of "*serious incident*" includes occurrences of malfunctions when their consequences meet the requirements of serious incidents as defined in Article 3(49).

Without this clarification, it will be misleading to state that malfunctions are not incidents, as then each obligation regarding incidents will have to be explained

³ ISO 31073:2022 Risk management — Vocabulary <https://www.iso.org/standard/79637.html>

explicitly to also apply to malfunctions. The MDR (Medical Devices Regulation)⁴ correctly sidesteps this issue by explicitly noting that malfunctions are incidents, and that they are the responsibilities of the relevant actors.

(10) A malfunction can be understood as any function of the AI system not performing as intended or a situation where an AI system fails to uphold the performance stated by the provider in the technical documentation (Article 11 AI Act), for its intended purpose and reasonably foreseeable misuse.

This statement should be rephrased for clarity. It should also indicate whose intention is being described. For example, would a deployer's intention being different suffice for a malfunction if it differs from a provider's (from the provider's perspective)? Though the AI Act Article 25(1)(c) states such changes in intended purpose may qualify the deployer also becoming a provider, this relies on an assessment of "*change in intended purpose*" which may not be reached when only considering "*intention*", and leads to a complex process to determine the answer.

To resolve this, we recommend stating: "*A malfunction can be understood as the AI system's performance, as defined in Article 3(18), not achieving its intended purpose, as defined in Article 3(12)*", which is implied by the last part of the existing sentence, but is clearer with the rephrasing by relying on established definitions of "*intended purpose*" and "*performance*". This also provides a clear indication that malfunctions are when the "*performance*" is not achieving the "*intended purpose*", which the guidelines aim to indicate. Additionally, this helps the obligation for both the providers and deployers to consider the '*capacity*' for achieving the intended purpose as part of the '*performance*' of the model, such as those indicated by Article 10 and Recital 67 regarding data governance. The use of Article 11 should be removed as it does not include discussed concepts (i.e. malfunction, intended purpose, and performance).

(11) In practice, the distinction between "incident" and "malfunction" in the AI Act should not be understood as a strict distinction, but rather as an emphasis on the importance of malfunctions in the context of incident monitoring.

This statement should be combined with Paragraph (9) so as to provide clarity within the same paragraph regarding the concepts of incident and malfunction.

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/745/oj>

3. Examples - Incident & Malfunction

These comments relate to Question 2 within the consultation form.

(12) Examples of incidents or malfunctions include:

- Misclassifications
- Significant drops in accuracy
- Temporary system downtime
- Unexpected system behaviour

The examples should be split into two paragraphs, with the first paragraph indicating malfunctions (as currently provided) and the second indicating incidents (as consequential harms that can arise from malfunctions). The current examples do not assist in achieving clarity for how these would classify as serious incidents as indicated in Paragraph (5), nor do they support the meaning of incidents as "*generally defined by their actual or potential negative consequences, particularly (potential) harm to humans or critical systems*" in Paragraph (8).

Since Paragraph (13) provides such examples, we recommend restructuring as follows:

- Section 2.3 starts with Paragraph (12) stating the causal nature of malfunctions and incidents becoming serious incidents.
- Paragraph (13) then provides examples of incidents and malfunctions which occur, and then
- Paragraph (14) can indicate examples of how these become serious incidents.

(13) The incident or malfunction needs to be causal, or likely to be causal, for the serious harms specified in Article 3(49) AI Act (Article 73(2) AI Act). The incident or malfunction is causal if, without it, the harm in its concrete form would not have occurred (or reasonably likely respectively more probable not to have occurred). The causation can also be indirect, i.e. secondary effects. Indirect examples include:

- An AI system provides an incorrect analysis of medical imaging, leading a physician to make an incorrect diagnosis or treatment decision, which subsequently causes harm to the patient.
- An AI based credit scoring system incorrectly flags the unreliability of a person and a loan is denied based on this decision.
- An AI system classifies a patient incorrectly as low risk, leading to a doctor not detecting a health condition which otherwise would have been easily identified.
- An AI based recruitment system checks CVs received and discards highly qualified candidates because of their gender or ethnicity and the hiring

organisation only pursues applications that have passed the AI based first check.

The examples provided are not sufficiently clear as being "*indirect effects*". For clarity, there should be a more detailed explanation of each as important obligations rely on their comprehension, and we suggest following the style used by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) in its guidelines when dealing with examples where each example has clarification text regarding its implications or justifying its categorisation.

In the examples, it is important to explicitly and clearly indicate how the "*indirect effects*" are being depicted and should be recognised. These should not be examples where the AI system is itself involved in creating the final outcome but has an intermediate human or process which does not have the ability to change the outcome. Thus, the indirect effects should be clear that there are mechanisms through which the outcome could have changed, and that the AI system has a causal relation to the outcome if it occurs.

We also ask for the guidelines to be clear that it should be considered as direct effects where AI systems are intended, by design and during operation, to be used by a human operator and where the human operator cannot override or change the decisions.

We also ask the examples to state that the involvement of the AI system would be the same regardless of correctness i.e. it would continue to have a causal relation and direct/indirect effects. Therefore these concepts are not limited to only the determination of incidents and malfunctions, but are an aspect of the use of the AI system as designed and when used within the deployment. Even if the AI system is "*correct*" it would still classify as an incident as the criteria for such incidents is "*harm*" and not "*correctness*" in accordance with the AI Act Article 3(49). This is a vital aspect of the AI Act's obligations regarding risk management and fundamental rights impact assessments.

We go through each example to indicate changes and clarifications.

(13) (a) An AI system provides an incorrect analysis of medical imaging, leading a physician to make an incorrect diagnosis or treatment decision, which subsequently causes harm to the patient.

Suggested rephrasing: *An AI system provides an incorrect analysis of **existing** medical imaging, which a physician **uses** to make a ~~incorrect~~ diagnosis or treatment decision, which subsequently causes harm to the patient.*

Here, it should be clarified that the AI system is used on an existing medical image and that the AI system itself is not involved in creating the image as otherwise it would classify as a direct effect due to the reliance on the AI system for the image. Similarly, the phrasing of "leading to" should be replaced with "uses" to indicate that the physician has the option of ignoring or deviating from the analysis, as otherwise if the physician is using the analysis as it stands then the AI system's outputs would be considered a direct effect.

(13) (b) An AI based credit scoring system incorrectly flags the unreliability of a person and a loan is denied based on this decision.

Suggested rephrasing: *An AI based credit scoring system ~~incorrectly~~ flags the ~~unreliability~~ **repayment risk** of the person **with a bias against certain groups** and a **bank manager uses this to deny a loan, which causes the person harm due to unfair discrimination.***

The use of the AI system is not clear in the example, as the denial of the loan could happen directly based on the "unreliability" indicator without any further process or intervention. This would then classify as a direct effect. Instead, the rephrasing clarifies that the AI system highlights a risk based on an discriminatory bias and that the decision is made by a person outside the AI system but where the outputs of the AI system are involved in the decision. This therefore classifies as a causal relation and as an indirect effect.

We also highlight that there is no criteria to "correctly" assess reliability of a person in general, and this example veers into being pseudoscience and implying that AI systems can correctly assess reliability. Instead, the rephrased example clarifies that the score produced is unfair by being discriminatory with respect to personal characteristics.

(13) (c) An AI system classifies a patient incorrectly as low risk, leading to a doctor not detecting a health condition which otherwise would have been easily identified.

Suggested rephrasing: *An AI system classifies a patient incorrectly as low risk **for a specific health indicator**, ~~leading to a~~ **which when used by a doctor causes a misdiagnosis by not detecting a health condition** ~~which otherwise would have been easily identified.~~*

(13) (d) An AI based recruitment system checks CVs received and discards highly qualified candidates because of their gender or ethnicity and the hiring organisation only pursues applications that have passed the AI based first check.

Suggested rephrasing: *An AI based recruitment system ~~checks~~ **analyses** CVs received and **produces a biased selection that** discards highly qualified candidates because of their gender or ethnicity **that would otherwise have been selected**, and the hiring organisation only pursues applications that have passed the AI based first check **leading to a discriminatory hiring outcome**.*

As with the earlier examples, the rephrasing clarifies the issue at hand and the harm in concrete terms, thereby providing sufficient clarity on the causality involved. Without this rephrasing, the ambiguity in the current phrasing can cause confusion as to the AI system making decisions and why this would be an indirect effect.

4. Definition - Causality & Harm

These comments relate to Question 4 within the consultation form.

(14) The direct or indirect causations should be limited to cases in which the AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose and reasonably foreseeable misuse, and the incident is not due to the wrong, unexpected use and unexpected errors by the system-users.

The guidance is misleading in the second part where it states "*incident is not due to the wrong, unexpected use and unexpected errors by the system-users*". This is because such wrong or unexpected uses or errors by the users can occur in context of not having sufficient information to operate the AI system or to be sufficiently informed so as to create such incidents. The AI Act Article 3(15) states "*instructions for use*" as including "*information provided by the provider to inform the deployer of, in particular, an AI system's intended purpose and **proper use***". Recital 91 further states "*deployers should ensure that the persons assigned to implement the instructions for use and human oversight as set out in this Regulation have the **necessary competence**, in particular **an adequate level of AI literacy, training** and authority to properly fulfil those tasks*". Recital 72 notes "*Providers should ensure that all documentation, including the instructions for use, **contains meaningful, comprehensive, accessible and understandable information**, taking into account the needs and foreseeable knowledge of the target deployers*". This means that if an incident were to occur based on a wrong or unexpected use or error on part of the system user, it must be first determined whether this occurred due to the deficiencies in the instructions or training or knowledge provided to the users prior to the incident. If affirmative, then this should also be considered as an incident or malfunction, partly to be consistent in regards to the obligation of the provider and deployer in ensuring the appropriate operation of the AI system which includes its use by users.

If user errors or incorrect uses which arise due to deficiencies in training or knowledge or capability are not considered an AI system incident, then it implies that the users are responsible for the incident and not the AI system, which would be incorrect. It also implies that were such user-led incidents happening regularly or at scale, this would not be monitored even if they are causing serious harm. This would be antithetical to the AI Act's intended protections. There is also a likelihood that the AI systems are being used by end-users (i.e. lay persons) who are not competent and who may not have sufficient AI literacy or capabilities to use the AI system without producing errors. To give an example, consider the medical imaging example in Paragraph (13) where the physician is using the AI system to form a diagnosis. If the AI system works correctly in terms of producing outputs, but the instructions to the physician state an incorrect interpretation of the output, then the physician's diagnosis will be incorrect due to the AI system's instructions, and therefore due to the AI system itself. Similarly, if a smartphone app claims to detect jaundice using "*AI-powered imaging*" and asks the person to take a photo of their eyes, and if the user happens to take a photo in a yellow light environment, the app may misdiagnose the user while claiming the user made an "*error*" by not taking a "*correct picture*". Regardless of the correct interpretation of the AI Act, which would be costly and time-consuming, the incident (assuming it evolves into a serious incident) would not be reported due to the guidelines.

We note that Article 3(13) defines "*reasonably foreseeable misuse*" as "*may result from reasonably foreseeable human behaviour*", and that such misuses occurring from human behaviour should therefore include errors or mistakes that a human may make due to having insufficient knowledge or capacity to operate the AI system. If the paragraph is left as is, it implies that the users are now a scapegoat for blaming the incidents on by declaring their use as "*wrong*" or "*unexpected*" and therefore not classifying this as an incident. Wrong or unexpected inputs or operations are typical and expected when testing technologies, and AI is no exception. Therefore, these are to be considered as "*reasonably foreseeable*" unless demonstrated otherwise.

We therefore recommend Paragraph (15) to be rephrased as follows: "*The direct or indirect causations should be limited to cases in which the AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose and reasonably foreseeable misuse, **including incidents due to the wrong ~~unexpected~~ use and ~~unexpected~~ errors by the system-users unless these are justified as being unforeseeable.***"

(15) Serious harm to person's health can include:

- a life-threatening illness or injury
- temporary or permanent impairment of a body structure or a body function

- a condition necessitating hospitalisation or prolongation of existing hospitalization
- medical or surgical intervention to prevent the first two examples. Examples of this can be:
 - professional medical care or additional unplanned medical treatment
 - a clinically relevant increase in the duration of a surgical procedure
- a chronic disease or serious psychological disease (a disease is serious when it impairs a person from significant life activities, including day-to-day functioning).
- foetal distress, foetal death or any congenital abnormality (including congenital physical or mental impairment) or birth defects.

All these are examples of physical harms, and the guidelines should also note the potential for AI systems to cause other harms to the health of the person. This is necessary as Article 3(1) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights refers to "*physical and mental integrity*", and Article 32 refers to "*mental (development)*". More broadly, we also refer to examples under "*psychological harms*", which can arise due to the direct effects of using an AI system by being subjected to certain outputs that cause mental distress or other forms of psychological trauma. There is a body of work within EU law that considers '*distress*' which is a non-physical (and non-material) harm, such as C-655/23 and also C-340/21 which is relevant for the '*causal*' relation between the AI system and the harm. We therefore ask for such examples in the guidelines regarding the non-physical harms produced by use of AI systems.

An example of how regulations across the world are adapting mental harms arising from AI systems is the Californian SB-243 Bill (adopted)⁵ which includes obligations to report incidents regarding '*suicidal ideation*' (i.e. suicidal thoughts) which are detected when a person is interaction with an "*AI Companion*" (or AI system under the AI Act). The risk of a person self-harming is (also) considered a psychological issue even if the self-harm itself takes a physical form such as injury or death. Therefore incidents should not be limited to when physical harms occur, but also when such mental or psychological precursors occur without necessitating them to lead to physical harms.

For reference, Recital 29 of the AI Act refers to AI's influence on human behaviour, and includes acknowledgement of risks such as persuasion, deception, and subversion of autonomy and decision-making. The Recital in the following statement notes, "*significant harms, in particular having sufficiently important adverse impacts on physical, psychological health or financial interests are likely to occur, are particularly dangerous and should therefore be prohibited*". Article 5 then provides a list of

⁵ https://leginfo.ca.gov/faces/billTextClient.xhtml?bill_id=202520260SB243

prohibited practices, which only apply to AI systems that meet the specified criteria. Other AI systems that are similar but are not prohibited should qualify for the notification of serious incidents. For example, AI systems that produce content that causes mental anguish to the person using it or when other people are subjected to it intentionally, and where the resulting psychological harm can be considered a serious impairment to the person's mental health and well being.

5. Incidents in Critical Infrastructure

These comments relate to Question 5 within the consultation form.

(19) The AI Act does not provide a threshold for when a disruption is considered to be serious. The CER and Recital 55 of the AI Act provide orientation. Under the AI Act a disruption is to be considered serious if for example:

- The disruption might result in an imminent threat to life or the physical safety of a person, including through serious harm to the provision of basic supplies to the population or to the exercise of the core function of the State

In this clarification, the Recital 55 does not restrict its statements to "*physical safety of a person*". The statements used in Recital 55 are "*protect the physical integrity of critical infrastructure or the health and safety of persons*" and "*might directly lead to risks to the physical integrity of critical infrastructure and thus to risks to health and safety of persons and property*". In both statements, Recital 55 talks about the general notion of health and safety, which includes both physical and mental aspects, and not only physical safety as noted in the guidelines. Therefore the guidelines should be updated to reflect "*health and safety of a person*" without limiting the impact only to physical safety.

(26) Only those infringements that significantly interfere with Charter-protected rights on a large scale, should be reportable.

The guidelines do not provide an indication of how to assess the scale of incidents. While the AI Act's "*serious incidents*" and its 3 Member States requirements can be one criteria, we recommend reusing the established incident assessment framework under the GDPR for its impact assessments (Article 34 and 35). The guidance on this is

available in the Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA)⁶ and determining whether processing is “*likely to result in a high risk*”, which have been endorsed by the EDPB.⁷ The guidance provides criteria such as scale of data subjects, volume of data, geographical extent, and duration, which should be adapted for the assessments under the AI Act.

6. Horizontal aspects for other regulations

These comments relate to Question 28 within the consultation form.

The AI Act's reporting obligations have similarity with other regulations, such as those within GDPR for data breach and those within NIS2 for security incidents. The consultation asked whether there can be a reduction in the reporting based on equivalence between the AI Act's reporting requirements and those from other regulations. The AIAL's comments are as below.

For GDPR Article 33, the obligations are equivalent 'sometimes' as the AI Act's definition for "*serious incidents*" does not account for (general) harms to fundamental rights, and therefore the GDPR obligation is broader as it is based on "*risk to rights*". Therefore, there are potential additional reporting obligations that differ between GDPR and AI Act.

For NIS2 Article 23, the obligations are equivalent 'sometimes' as NIS2 uses the criteria "*considerable*" which is broader than the AI Act' "*serious incident*" criteria. Notably, Article 23 includes "*non-material*" explicitly whereas the AI Act does not. NIS2, like GDPR, also is based on the assessment of "*risks*" for the incident to occur. Therefore, there are potential additional reporting obligations that differ between NIS2 and AI Act.

2. Incident Reporting Template

These comments relate to Question 38 within the consultation form regarding the incident reporting template published with the guidelines.⁸

Section 1 Administrative information

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/611236/en>

⁷ https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/data-protection-impact-assessments-high-risk-processing_en

⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/consultations/ai-act-commission-issues-draft-guidance-and-reporting-template-serious-ai-incidents-and-seeks>

- Section 1, which is intended for administrative information, should also include a field or indicator for whether the reporting is within the defined timeframe or is delayed or late and justification.
- 1.2.6 (titled section Date, type, and classification of incident report) should include an information box for summary of the harm, and should be a multiple select.
- 1.3 (titled section Submitter information) should include a field for Member State for each entity as this is essential for administration and co-ordination. Address should be a separate field.
- 1.3.3 (titled Authorised representative information) and 1.3.4 (titled section Submitter's details if not also provider or authorised representative) should include field explaining relationship between representative and company (e.g. DPO, consultant).
- 1.3.5 (titled Information about other incident obligations) should include fields for name of reported entity and under which law together in one box. Separation leads to confusion where relation between entities being competent authority under a particular law would not be specified.
- Optionally 1.3.5 field can also provide information under which clause of relevant law for co-ordination
- 1.3.5. should also include an option to indicate whether the notification to other bodies included additional information not provided in this report.

Section 2 AI System information

- 2.2 (titled Description of system and commercial information) Should include a field for whether the AI system has been substantially modified or not, whether it has undergone specific certifications, and whether the system is being used current i.e. is in operation or has been paused or halted for the moment following the incident.

Section 3 Incident information

- 3.1 (titled Nature of incident) should include who has been harmed or been affected in the incident; and whether this is reversible and with how much effort;

- 3.1 should also include whether there is a likelihood for the incident to be repeated and the extent of velocity i.e. how quickly the incident materialises;
- 3.1 should also include the scale of people already affected and the scale of those who are at risk of being affected;
- 3.1 should also include whether the incident can lead to additional incidents outside the organisation's control.
- 3.2 (titled AI System information) the field for estimated number of affected should be moved to 3.1 as part of incident information ;
- 3.2 should include a field to state whether there has been a change in the AI system after the incident e.g. it is paused or stopped following the incident (we note that mitigations are to be specified in section 4, but still consider this information to be essential to understand the continued risk of same or associated incidents to materialise)
- 3.3 (titled Initial reporter) should indicate whether the reporter is the organisation or external person i.e. is this a public report.

Section 4 Provider analysis

- 4.1 (titled Provider's preliminary comments) should include a separate field for measures in place before the incident which were intended to address the incident and their effectiveness, and then a separate field for the actions taken after the incident (as in 4.1.B).
- 4.2 (titled Cause investigation and conclusion) should be asking about impact assessment as these are serious incidents and we are dealing with significant harms to people and entities. With this in mind, there should be additional fields to ask about what mitigations are planned to minimise or address the harms and to prevent specific harms from the same incident occurring again in the future which is distinct from 4.1.B which only enquires about initial actions.
- 4.2 should also have an assessment of whether this incident was preventable i.e. it could have been avoided, and if yes, then how, and whether there have been measures taken to ensure this for future.
- We note that these additional requirements and perspectives are in line with the reporting obligations under GDPR (Article 33) and NIS2 (Article 23) and therefore are expected within the framework of EU legislations and do not represent an overreach of reporting requirements. We also note that this information would be necessary to be identified for the provider or deployer, as relevant, as part of their risk and impact assessments. Therefore we consider this information being documented as being a good measure that supports

accountability and ensures the organisation is equipped to handle serious incidents.

Section 5 General comments

Submission of this report does not represent a conclusion by the provider and / or authorised representative or the market surveillance authority that the content of this report is complete or accurate, that the AI system(s) listed failed in any manner and/or that the AI system(s) caused or contributed to the alleged serious incident.

"Submission... does not represent a conclusion ... that the content of this report is complete or accurate" - this means the report cannot be relied upon as evidence as it is asserted as not being accurate. This is futile as an obligation and as a measure for accountability, and it should be changed. We suggest rephrasing this as *"The submitter acknowledges the report is complete and accurate as known to the submitter at the moment of submission and changes identified in the future will be submitted through a separate report if relevant"*.

Similarly, *"the AI system(s) listed failed in any manner and/or that the AI system(s) caused or contributed to the alleged serious incident"* is also not a good statement for accountability. Instead, this should read, *"The submitter acknowledges the report only provides information about the incident and that the information is not intended to describe the causality of the AI system(s) involved without further information or investigation"*.

~ END ~